

Molecular Characterization and Phylogenetic Analysis of *Sclerotium rolfsii* Isolates from Sunflowers Affected by Collar Rot Disease in the Southern Coastal Region of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the genetic diversity among *Sclerotium rolfsii* isolates causing collar rot disease in sunflowers from the southern coastal region of Bangladesh, based on DNA sequences of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region. PCR amplification of the ITS region was performed using the universal forward primer ITS1 and reverse primer ITS4. For most fungal isolates, the amplified ITS region measured approximately 610 to 630 base pairs in length. The sequences demonstrated 92.36% to 100% similarity with existing sequences in the NCBI GenBank database. The DNA sequences of the *S. rolfsii* isolates were submitted to NCBI, where they were assigned GenBank accession numbers as follows: PP908469 for isolate BAHaSr-1, PP908470 for isolate GAHaSr-2, PP908474 for isolate GKHaSr-1, PP908476 for isolate DaKHaSr-1, PP908473 for isolate DPHaSr-1, PP908478 for isolate DKHaSr-2, PP908477 for isolate PaKHaSr-1, PP908472 for isolate PhaKHaSr-1, PP908475 for isolate TKHaSr-1, and PP908471 for isolate MKHaSr-1. Phylogenetic analysis revealed that most isolates in clade 1 clustered into subgroup 1, while the remaining isolates formed subgroup 2, indicating distinct genetic relationships. Notably, isolates BAHaSr-1, PhaKHaSr-1, MKHaSr-1, and DPHaSr-1 exhibited a high degree of similarity with *S. rolfsii* isolate KACC45483 C9 (accession no. OR981874). In contrast, isolates GKHaSr-1, DaKHaSr-1, TKHaSr-1, PaKHaSr-1, DKHaSr-2, and GAHaSr-2 were closely related to *S. rolfsii* isolate GKVK=beetroot (accession no. MW350729).

Keywords: Genetic diversity, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, DNA Extraction, Sequencing, Phylogenetic tree.

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Introduction

Collar rot disease, caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii*, is a destructive soil-borne fungal pathogen that infects a wide range of crops, including sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*), leading to significant agricultural losses worldwide. In Bangladesh, particularly in the southern coastal regions, sunflower cultivation is gaining popularity due to its ability to thrive in saline-affected soils. However, the widespread prevalence of collar rot disease poses a significant threat to sunflower production, potentially causing yield losses of 50-80% under conditions favorable to the pathogen (Dasgupta et al., 2020). This underscores the urgent need for in-depth studies to better understand the pathogen.

Sclerotium rolfsii is infamous for its ability to infect over 500 plant species, with its sclerotia capable of surviving in soil for prolonged periods, making disease management particularly challenging (Aycock, 1966). The pathogen's persistence and spread are further facilitated by environmental factors such as warm, moist conditions characteristics typical of Bangladesh's coastal regions creating an ideal environment for the proliferation of *S. rolfsii* (Meena et al., 2015). Despite its economic and agricultural significance, research on the molecular characterization of *S. rolfsii* isolates from sunflower plants in the southern coastal region of Bangladesh remains limited.

Molecular characterization and phylogenetic analysis are crucial for understanding the genetic diversity and evolutionary relationships among pathogen isolates. This knowledge is essential for developing disease-resistant crop varieties and implementing effective disease management strategies (Anderson and Carbone, 2014). Techniques such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), sequencing of internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions, and phylogenetic analysis have been widely utilized to differentiate fungal pathogens at the species level and to analyze their genetic diversity (White et al., 1990). For *S. rolfsii*, molecular markers such as ITS and rDNA have proven effective in characterizing genetic variation among isolates (Punja, 1985).

In this study, we conducted molecular characterization and phylogenetic analysis of *S. rolfsii* isolates collected from sunflower plants affected by collar rot in the southern coastal region of Bangladesh. The primary objective was to investigate the genetic diversity of *S. rolfsii* isolates and explore their evolutionary relationships using molecular markers. Through phylogenetic analysis, we aimed to identify the genetic lineages of the pathogen in this region, providing insights into its potential origin, spread, and adaptation. These findings could enhance our understanding of the pathogen's biology and support the development of effective disease control strategies, which are urgently needed to sustain sunflower production in Bangladesh.

This research was undertaken to address the knowledge gap concerning the molecular characteristics of *S. rolfsii* in Bangladesh, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of collar rot disease epidemiology and supporting the development of effective strategies to mitigate its impact on sunflower cultivation.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted in the molecular laboratory of the Plant Pathology Division, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh, to analyze molecular variation among selected *Sclerotium rolfsii* isolates through molecular characterization. Similarity searches for nucleotide sequences were performed using BLAST on the NCBI website

(<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) to match the sequences with existing entries in the NCBI GenBank database for the identification of *S. rolfsii* isolates. Additionally, a phylogenetic tree was constructed with closely related *S. rolfsii* sequences to examine the genetic relationships among the isolates.

DNA Extraction

Fungal isolates were grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA) for four days, after which the fungal mycelia were harvested using a needle and placed in a mortar and pestle. DNA extraction from the fungal isolates was performed using a Promega DNA extraction kit with slight modifications. A quick DNA extraction method was adapted from Collado-Romero et al. (2006). The fungal mycelia were dried on a clean bench for 30 minutes, transferred to 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tubes, and stored at -20°C for further analysis. To extract DNA, the mycelia were ground in a mortar and pestle with 600 µl of nuclei solution, gently pressing the mycelia to create a paste. The paste was transferred to a 2 ml micro centrifuge tube, incubated at 65°C in a water bath for 15 minutes, and centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 5 minutes. Next, 4 µl of RNase enzyme solution was added to the tube, which was incubated at 37°C in a water bath for 15 minutes, then cooled to room temperature. Subsequently, 100 µl of protein precipitation solution was added to the tube, vortexed vigorously for 20 seconds, placed on ice for 5 minutes, and centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 3 minutes. The supernatant was transferred to a new 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tube, and an equal volume of isopropanol was added. The tube was gently mixed by inverting it six times and centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was discarded, and 500 µl of 75% ethanol was added to the tube, followed by centrifugation at 12,000 rpm for 5 minutes. The ethanol was removed, and a second washing step was performed using 75% ethanol, centrifuging for 10 seconds at 8,000 rpm. The DNA pellet was dried completely on a clean bench, and 100 µl of nuclease free water was added to the micro centrifuge tube. The DNA pellet was dissolved by incubating the tube in a water bath at 65°C for 20 minutes and then stored at -20°C for future use.

PCR Amplification

PCR amplification was performed using ITS1 and ITS4 primers to target the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region for species level identification of the isolates (White et al., 1990; Alam et al., 2020). The universal forward primer ITS1 (5' TCC GTA GGT GAA CCT GCGG 3') and reverse primer ITS4 (5' TCC TCC GCT TAT TGA TATGC 3') were used for amplifying the ITS regions (White et al., 1990). The PCR reaction mixture had a total volume of 25 µl, consisting of 12.5 µl PCR master mix, 1 µl ITS1 forward primer (10 µmol), 1 µl ITS4 reverse primer (10 µmol), 1 µl DNA sample, and 9.5 µl nuclease free water. PCR cycling conditions were initial denaturation at 95°C for 2 minutes (1 cycle), denaturation at 95°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 55°C for 30 seconds, and extension at 72°C for 30 seconds (repeated for 34 cycles) and final extension at 72°C for 10 minutes.

Agarose Gel Electrophoresis and DNA Purification

Agarose gel electrophoresis was performed to qualitatively assess the genomic DNA samples. High quality DNA appeared as a single, distinct band. The procedure was carried out using a submarine horizontal agarose gel apparatus (Bangalore Genei) as described by Sambrook et al. (1989). To prepare the gel, 1.0% (w/v) agarose was dissolved in 1.0X TAE buffer by boiling for 5 minutes. After cooling slightly, the solution was poured into an electrophoresis tray fitted with a comb to create wells and allowed to solidify at room temperature. Once the gel solidified, the comb was carefully removed, and the gel was placed in an electrophoresis tank filled with 1.0X TAE buffer. For sample preparation, 2 µl of loading dye was mixed with 4 µl of the DNA sample, and the mixture was loaded into the wells. The gel was run at a constant voltage of 50 V for one hour. After electrophoresis, DNA bands were visualized using a gel documentation system (Alpha Digidoc, USA), and images of the gel were captured for record-keeping.

The PCR products were purified using a QIAquick PCR Purification Kit after electrophoresis. The genomic DNA isolated through the above methods contained small amounts of RNA and protein

contaminants. RNA contamination was removed by treating the DNA with RNase that was free of DNase. Additional deproteinization steps were then performed to eliminate residual RNase and proteins, ensuring the removal of most contaminants.

Figure 1. Agarose Gel Electrophoresis Picture of PCR Amplified ITS Region for Different Isolates of *Sclerotium rolfsii*, Where L1= Molecular marker (100), L2= negative control, L3= BAHaSr-1, L4= GAHaSr-2, L5= GKHaSr-1, L6= DaKHaSr-1, L7= DPHaSr-1, L8= DKHaSr-2, L9= PaKHaSr-1, L10= PhaKHaSr-1, L11= TKHaSr-1, L12= MKHaSr-1.

DNA Sequencing and Analysis

The PCR products were sequenced using the primers mentioned above, on an Applied Biosystems 3130 sequencer (www.appliedbiosystems.com), following the procedure described by Sanger et al. (1977). Sanger sequencing was performed at the National Institute of Biotechnology (NIB), Bangladesh, using purified DNA. The resulting sequences were compared by blasting the data against the NCBI database using BLASTn. The sequences generated in this study have been deposited in GenBank, and the corresponding accession numbers are available.

Development of Phylogenetic Tree

The phylogenetic tree was constructed to examine the evolutionary relationships of the fungal isolates with reference strains. The alignment and tree construction were performed using TreeBASE (<http://purl.org/phylo/treebase/phyloids/study/TB2:S23108>). Evolutionary analyses were conducted using MEGA X (Kumar et al., 2018).

Results and Discussion

PCR Amplification

Total DNA was extracted from the mycelia of pure cultures of *Sclerotium rolfsii* isolates. After DNA extraction, the fungal DNA was used as a template for PCR amplification, using the universal forward primer ITS1 (5' TCC GTA GGT GAA CCT GCGG 3') and the reverse primer ITS4 (5' TCC TCC GCT TAT TGA TATGC 3') to amplify the ITS regions. For most of the fungal isolates, the ITS regions were approximately 610 to 630 base pairs in length (Fig. 1).

Sequencing and Analysis

The PCR purified products were sent to the National Institute of Biotechnology, Savar, Dhaka, for sequencing. Sequencing was performed using the reverse primer ITS4 (5' TCC TCC GCT TAT TGA TATGC 3') on an automated sequencer. Sequence similarity was determined using BLASTn on the NCBI website (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>), where the sequences were compared with existing DNA sequences in the NCBI GenBank to identify the fungal isolates. The sequence similarity ranged from 92.36% to 100% (Table 1).

Table 1. Sequence Similarity of *Sclerotium rolfsii* Isolates Using the BLASTn

Isolates	Base pairs (bp)	Accession Number	% matched with <i>S. rolfsii</i>
BAHaSr-1	630	PP908469	100
GAHaSr-2	630	PP908470	100
GKHaSr-1	630	PP908474	99.37
DaKHaSr-1	630	PP908476	95.73
DPHaSr-1	630	PP908473	100
DKHaSr-2	620	PP908478	92.36
PaKHaSr-1	630	PP908477	94.42
PhaKHaSr-1	620	PP908472	100
TKHaSr-1	610	PP908475	98.67
MKHaSr-1	630	PP908471	100

Deposition of Nucleotide Sequences in GenBank of NCBI

The DNA sequences of the *Sclerotium rolfsii* isolates were submitted to the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) for deposition in GenBank and to obtain accession numbers. The GenBank accession numbers for the *Sclerotium rolfsii* isolates were presented in Table 1, where Accession no. PP908469 for *Sclerotium rolfsii* isolate BAHaSr-1, PP908470 for *S. rolfsii* isolate GAHaSr-2, PP908474 for *S. rolfsii* isolate GKHaSr-1, PP908476 for *S. rolfsii* isolate DaKHaSr-1, PP908473 for *S. rolfsii* isolate DPHaSr-1, PP908478 for *S. rolfsii* isolate DKHaSr-2, PP908477 for *S. rolfsii* isolate PaKHaSr-1, PP908472 for *S. rolfsii* isolate PhaKHaSr-1, PP908475 for *S. rolfsii* isolate TKHaSr-1, PP908471 for *S. rolfsii* isolate MKHaSr-1.

Genetic Diversity of the Isolates of *Sclerotium rolfsii*

To assess genetic diversity, a phylogenetic tree of the *Sclerotium rolfsii* isolates was constructed using available ITS sequences of *S. rolfsii* from the NCBI database. The tree grouped the isolates into different clades (Fig. 2). The majority of the isolates in clade 1 formed subgroup 1, while the remaining isolates were placed in subgroup 2, indicating distinct relationships. Among the isolates, *S. rolfsii* isolates BAHaSr-1, PhaKHaSr-1, MKHaSr-1, and DPHaSr-1 were highly similar to *S. rolfsii* isolate KACC45483 C9 (accession no. OR981874), while isolates GKHaSr-1, DaKHaSr-1, TKHaSr-1, PaKHaSr-1, DKHaSr-2, and GAHaSr-2 were closely related to *S. rolfsii* isolate GKVK-beetroot (accession no. MW350729).

Collar rot disease, caused by the fungus *Sclerotium rolfsii*, is a major issue affecting various crops worldwide, particularly sunflowers (*Helianthus annuus*) in the southern coastal region of Bangladesh. This region, characterized by saline-affected soils, is increasingly being used for sunflower cultivation. However, the widespread prevalence of collar rot disease, compounded by warm and moist conditions, poses a significant threat to sunflower production, potentially causing yield losses of up to 80% in some cases (Dasgupta et al., 2020). Given the economic importance of sunflowers and the damage caused by this disease, molecular characterization and phylogenetic analysis of *S. rolfsii* isolates are crucial for understanding the genetic diversity and relationships among these fungal populations.

Figure 2. Phylogenetic Neighbor Joining Tree of *Sclerotium rolfsii* Isolates Based on Internal Transcribed Spacer Region of Ribosomal DNA with that of Available Isolates in the GenBank of National Center for Biotechnology Information Database Using MEGA 5.2 Software with 1,000 Bootstrap Replicates. The Scale Bar is in Fixed Nucleotide Substitutions per Sequence Position

Molecular characterization has become an essential tool for understanding the genetic diversity and phylogenetic relationships of plant pathogens like *Sclerotium rolfsii*. The internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region of ribosomal DNA (rDNA) is widely used in molecular studies due to its high variability, making it an effective marker for distinguishing fungal species (White et al., 1990). In this study, *S. rolfsii* isolates were characterized based on ITS sequencing, with amplicons ranging from 610 to 630 base pairs (bp), a size consistent with previous studies on fungal genetic diversity using ITS (Meena et al., 2023). The use of universal primers ITS1 and ITS4 for amplification enabled precise identification of the isolates. The genetic sequences of the isolates were compared with those in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) GenBank database. The isolates showed 92.36% to 100% similarity with other *S. rolfsii* sequences, confirming that ITS regions are highly conserved across different *S. rolfsii* populations

(Paul et al., 2017). The submission of these sequences to GenBank and the assignment of accession numbers (e.g., PP908469 to PP908478) contribute to the expanding genetic database for this pathogen, supporting future research and enabling comparisons across various geographic regions.

The phylogenetic analysis in this study provided valuable insights into the genetic relationships between the *S. rolfsii* isolates. Phylogenetic trees constructed from ITS sequences revealed two major subgroups within the isolates, suggesting genetic divergence likely influenced by environmental factors and geographical separation. The clustering of isolates into distinct subgroups indicates that the pathogen may have undergone local adaptation, as some isolates were more closely related to one another than to others (Kumar et al., 2018). For example, isolates such as BAHaSr-1, MKHaSr-1, PhaKHaSr-1, and DPHaSr-1 were closely related to *S. rolfsii* isolate KACC45483 C9, while isolates such as GKHaSr-1, DaKHaSr-1, TKHaSr-1, and GAHaSr-2 showed a higher degree of similarity to *S. rolfsii* isolate GKVK-beetroot (accession no. MW350729). These findings align with previous studies that have identified multiple clades within *S. rolfsii* populations based on molecular markers (Mahadevakumar et al., 2015). Phylogenetic trees based on ITS sequences have been widely used to study the evolutionary relationships of fungal pathogens, providing evidence of both local diversification and the global spread of specific lineages (McDonald & McDermott, 1993; Punja, 1985). The distinct genetic relationships observed in this study reflect the pathogen's ability to adapt to different environmental conditions, which is critical for its survival in diverse agroecological zones, such as the saline soils of southern Bangladesh.

The ability of *S. rolfsii* to infect over 500 plant species, combined with its resilience in harsh environmental conditions, makes it a formidable pathogen (Aycock, 1966). Its survival is facilitated by the production of sclerotia dense, hardened structures that enable the fungus to persist in soil for extended periods, even in the absence of a host (Meena et al., 2015). These sclerotia germinate under favorable environmental conditions, such as high humidity and warm temperatures, which are characteristic of the southern coastal regions of Bangladesh.

The genetic diversity observed among the isolates in this study suggests that *S. rolfsii* populations are highly adaptable and capable of evolving in response to local environmental conditions. This genetic flexibility likely contributes to the difficulty of managing *S. rolfsii* in agricultural systems. Understanding the genetic diversity of *S. rolfsii* is therefore essential for developing effective disease management strategies, including the breeding of resistant sunflower varieties. Molecular studies like this one lay the groundwork for more targeted disease control approaches, such as identifying genetic markers associated with virulence or resistance (Anderson and Carbone, 2014).

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification and sequencing of the ITS region were the primary molecular techniques used in this study to characterize the fungal isolates. PCR is a widely established method for amplifying specific DNA regions, enabling the identification of organisms at the molecular level (Bruns et al., 1991). The ITS region, in particular, has been widely used for fungal identification due to its highly conserved nature within species, while still providing sufficient variability for differentiation between species (Tyson et al., 2002). The success of the PCR amplification in this study, with the majority of isolates producing clear bands of approximately 610–630 bp, demonstrates the reliability of ITS as a molecular marker for fungal pathogens (Alam et al., 2020). The use of agarose gel electrophoresis further allowed for the qualitative estimation of the DNA samples, ensuring that high-quality DNA was used for subsequent sequencing (Sambrook et al., 1989). Sequencing the PCR products provided precise genetic information essential for phylogenetic analysis and for comparing the isolates with other known *S. rolfsii* sequences in the GenBank database. This combination of molecular techniques has been successfully applied in other studies to investigate the genetic diversity of plant pathogens, highlighting its utility in fungal diagnostics and research (Okabe, 2001).

The molecular characterization and phylogenetic analysis of *S. rolfsii* isolates from sunflower plants in Bangladesh have several important implications. First, the observed genetic diversity among the isolates

underscores the pathogen's potential for rapid evolution, which may complicate efforts to control collar rot disease. Second, the identification of distinct genetic subgroups within the population suggests that the pathogen may be adapting to local environmental conditions, further highlighting the need for region specific disease management strategies. Future research should focus on expanding the sample size to include more isolates from different regions of Bangladesh and investigating the potential mechanisms underlying the pathogen's adaptability. Understanding how *S. rolfsii* interacts with various environmental factors, such as soil salinity and temperature, could provide valuable insights into its epidemiology and guide the development of more effective disease control measures. Additionally, molecular studies exploring the genetic basis of resistance in sunflower plants could aid in developing resistant crop varieties, offering a sustainable solution to managing collar rot disease.

Conclusions

This study was lead to highlight the critical role of molecular characterization and phylogenetic analysis in understanding the genetic diversity and adaptability of *Sclerotium rolfsii*, the causal agent of collar rot disease in sunflowers. The documentation of distinct genetic subgroups within the isolates underscores the pathogen's capacity for local adaptation, influenced by environmental issues such as soil salinity and temperature in southern Bangladesh. Sequencing of the ITS region provided valued insights into the genetic relationships among the isolates, contributing to the global database and paving the way for more precise diagnostics and targeted disease management strategies. Given the pathogen's resilience and economic impact, forthcoming research should prioritize expanding geographic sampling, exploring mechanisms of adaptability, and identifying genetic markers associated with virulence or resistance. These efforts will support the development of resistant sunflower varieties and region specific management strategies, proposing a sustainable approach to justifying the significant yield losses caused by collar rot disease.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding publication of this manuscript.

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